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Litsa Varonis

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STEAM WITH A GENDER PERSPECTIVE

Gema de Pablo González and Mariano Sanz-Prieto
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Introduction

Introducing the gender perspective in the different projects presented in this paper has its own reason for being. Year after year, the Spanish Ministry of Education and Vocational Training, in its yearly publication *Equality in Figures*, highlights the still existing inequality between boys and girls in the choice of science careers. In addition, the report gives the percentages in relation to other European countries and worldwide. In these percentages, the same concept persists: women and science do not seem to go hand in hand at the level they should (Ministerio de Educación y Formación Profesional, 2021).

In addition to the above data, the gender bias in the choice of STEM careers (Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics) in favour of men has been evident for several years now. Stoet & Geary (2018) insist on the persistence of this bias and the failure of the usual hypotheses to explain and mitigate it, forcing the search for new approaches. In this regard, the authors compare international data through reports such as the PISA 2015 Report (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development [OECD], 2016). The results show that in two out of three countries, girls are equal to or better than boys in science and are also well prepared to choose STEM studies, both at secondary and university level. However, the higher the equality bar in the country, the less women choose STEM careers, and consequently the gender bias increases. This is what the authors call the "*educational paradox of gender equality*", which means that the greater the equality, the greater the gap in STEM between women and men (Angulo, 2019).

Another study, which confirms the same data, refers to enrolment and degree completion data from Harvard and MIT Massive Open Courses, with students enrolled from 25 countries, where female enrolments are lower than male enrolments, but final completion is similar. Again, there is less gender bias and greater likelihood to enrol in less developed and less gender-equal countries (Jiang et al., 2018). Specifically, in Spain, of the enrolments made, 72% are men and 28% are women. Of these, 9.36% of enrolled men and 21.5% of enrolled women complete the course (Angulo, 2019).

These data are important in terms of the future of society we should be aiming for. Regardless of the gender bias, it has been observed that in recent years the number of young people studying science in Europe has declined (Robles et al., 2015). According to these authors, there is a difficulty in achieving a knowledge economy and scientific literacy among citizens. In this same perspective, Rocard et al. (2007) warn that the decline in interest in science lies in how it is being taught in schools. Thus, some authors such as Solbes (2011), Solbes Matarredona et al. (2007), and Lozano Lucia, (2012) have investigated the factors that are influencing dropout, as well as what innovative proposals could be addressed to tackle these attitudes. Results show that it is important to focus on compulsory education, where students have to pursue science studies without being able to drop out, but that this can be a key moment to motivate them or improve their attitude, and therefore their teaching should be improved to motivate them to learn.

If we add to these data the previously mentioned one about the gender gap in terms of science studies and skills, we must insist on including a perspective that reduces this gap. It is more than evident, and this is demonstrated by numerous studies (Bian et al., 2017; López-Navajas, 2014), that our society separates science from women, we can say that there is a gender stereotype where it is universally believed that women are less prepared for science and, especially some branches of science. In this sense, some data extracted from the Spanish Annual Report on equality figures of the Ministry of Education and Vocational Training 2021 quoted in Macho (2021) are to be expected, where we find that women choose more studies related to Education (77.9%) and Health and Social Services (71.8%). However, there is less presence in Engineering, Industry and Construction (29%) and Computer Science (13.4%).

In addition, the report also extracts other interesting data in relation to international data, such as, for example, a liking for mathematics, where 31% of female students in Spain say that they like it very much, compared to 42.7% of male students. In the European Union (EU) as a whole, 32.8% of girls and 44.1% of boys like math very much. In the OECD average, it is 32.9% and 41.5% (Macho, 2021). These data seem to us to be significant, since they indicate women are pushed away from careers linked to engineering, computer science and mathematics, while they continue to be leaders in sciences related to care and social services. The immediate consequence of these data is that the gender gap in the workplace will also increase, since the present and the future is and will be technological. It is therefore essential to tackle actions and projects that motivate and improve the figures for interest in science, both at a general level and for women and girls.

As a result of these studies and based on this perspective, we present below different Erasmus+ projects whose main objective is to bring science closer to the different school stages, and especially to female pupils.

Erasmus+ Projects about Gender and Steam

1. Science4Fun

The Science4Fun Project approaches science education as something fun and motivating, with the aim of generating educational resources to achieve this goal. As a European project, it involves partner organizations from different countries such as the Netherlands, Spain, Belgium, Portugal and Poland, whose experience is extensive in educational projects that promote the use of technology and teacher training, with the aim of providing them with more tools and resources in their classrooms. There is a need to develop projects and initiatives in the classroom that reduce the gender gap and encourage greater interest in scientific activities.

It is a 36-month project, which started in September 2018, co-funded by the Erasmus+ programme from the Netherlands agency. The project partners are:

- Stichting Kenniscentrum Pro Work (the Netherlands)
- Universidad Autónoma de Madrid (Spain)
- University of Humanities and Economics in Lodz (Poland)
- Fundación Siglo22 (Spain)
- JKVG vzw (Belgium)
- Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovacao (Portugal)
- Natsionalen ucheben tsentar (Bulgaria)
- Ljudska univerza Velenje (Eslovenia)
- Euroface Consulting s.r.o (Czech Republic)

The main objective of this project is to provide resources and tools so that science teachers can carry out their teaching work in a more attractive and motivating way. Specifically, the main objectives are to:

1. Make science fun for students.
2. Promote sciences among girls in order to improve the ratio of girls to boys in those studies.
3. Provide tools so that science teachers can achieve the above objectives.

All of this is materialized through a methodology that consists of five components, which will be described below.

1. Baseline tests

As part of the project, baseline tests have been designed to determine the state of knowledge of the pupils in the different schools participating in the project. This is not a curricular evaluation test, but a tool for observing, throughout the project, the evolution of the pupils in the subjects in question. The purpose of this action, therefore, is to know the evolution of the students' learning, by carrying out the baseline tests with them with a periodicity of approximately 6 months.

These tests are based on the main objectives of the European Qualification Framework (EQF) for lifelong learning (European Union, 2018). These are: to facilitate access to learning for learners and to enable mobility of learners between different countries of the European Union (The European Qualifications Framework (EQF) | Europass, n.d.). The EQF consists of eight levels in three domains: knowledge, skills and competences. Below is an extract from the framework for the EQF1 and EQF2 levels. (European Union, 2018)

Table 1

European Qualifications Framework: Excerpted Example

	KNOWLEDGE	SKILLS	COMPETENCES
	In the EQF, the knowledge is described as theoretical and/or factual.	In the EQF, skills are described as cognitive (use of logical, intuitive and creative thinking) and practical (based on manual dexterity and the use of methods, materials, tools and instruments).	In the EQF, competence is described in terms of responsibility and autonomy.
Level 1	Basic general knowledge.	Basic skills needed to perform simple tasks.	Work or study under direct supervision in a structured context.

	KNOWLEDGE	SKILLS	COMPETENCES
Level 2	Basic factual knowledge in a specific field of work or study.	Basic cognitive and practical skills needed to use useful information to perform tasks and solve common problems with the help of simple rules and tools.	Work or study under supervision with a certain degree of autonomy.

Note: Extracted from the European Qualifications Framework for lifelong learning. (EQF) - <https://europa.eu/europass/en/description-eight-efq-levels>

2. Educative Science Resources

Once the teachers obtain the results of the baseline test, they will have science educational resources to work with the students. The interest of this action is to achieve one of the objectives of the project, i.e. to make science fun and motivating.

3. Comparison among the Participant Countries

By carrying out the baseline tests in the different partner countries, it is possible to find out the situation of pupils in the different schools, both within and between countries. This is done in an aggregated and anonymous way.

4. Narrowing the Gender Gap in the Study of Science

One of the project's actions is to generate and encourage interest in science careers among girls, as data shows that there is a gender gap in this respect. In this sense, the project seeks to give visibility to women scientists throughout history and around the world. To create references so that girls can dream and choose to be scientists, just like their male peers. And for boys to learn to value the scientific knowledge of their female peers in the same way as their male counterparts.

5. Online Training

With the aim of training teachers in the use of different methodologies, resources and tools, an online training platform has been designed. The courses provided deal with topics such as how to change the learning paradigm, new assessment models, making women in science more visible, internet tools for teaching science and methodologies such as Problem Based Learning (PBL).

2. STEAMitUP

The “STEAMitUP” project aims to develop an interdisciplinary STEAM programme to train students, school leaders, school staff and school communities in the application of STEAM activities, robotics and digital tools to help develop students' 21st century skills (creativity, problem solving, self-esteem and collaboration). The project aims to develop an innovative e-learning space for school leaders and staff using blended methodologies (face-to-face, online and mobile), tools and activities.

The following partner countries are involved in this project: United Kingdom, Cyprus, Ireland, Greece, the Netherlands and Spain, in particular the following organizations:

- Lancaster and Morecambe College (United Kingdom)
- Centre for advancement of research and development in educational technology LTD-CARDET (Cyprus)
- Future in Perspective Limited (Ireland)
- Palladion Lykeion Ekfpaideuthria Douka (Greece)
- Rijksuniversiteit Groningen (the Netherlands)
- Fundación Siglo22 (Spain)

The main objectives of the STEAMitUP project are:

- Build the capacity of teachers, school leaders and school staff to organize and implement STEAM activities in schools using digital (such as robotics) and non-digital tools.
- Develop the digital skills, the creativity, problem solving skills, self-esteem and collaboration among the students.
- Encourage and motivate students to engage in STEAM fields while reducing the gender gap.

This is materialized through interactive and collaborative hands-on activities that allow personalization of the learning experience, as facilitated by digital technologies. As we know, these technologies offer new ways of organizing and structuring teaching and learning and new accessible learning environments that can motivate and engage learners. However, successfully harnessing their full potential for education is first and foremost a question of improving education.

The aim of STEAMitUP is therefore to develop the capacity of teachers, through technology, to implement innovative practical activities that develop skills and

competences in students. The project builds on other actions in which consortium members have been involved in the past, such as School on the Cloud, Making Learning, Science Fun, and Science Fiction in Education.

STEAMitUP focuses on leveraging STEAM subjects and robotics to develop students' critical skills through digital and non-digital tools.

The project also includes the development of a wide range of tools that will combine rich material for use by teachers and the training of teachers to use these innovative tools and to be able to use, adapt and localize the STEAMitUP toolkit.

To meet the above needs, multiple innovative aspects can be identified in the STEAMitUP project in terms of design, development and implementation:

- **Online platform.** The STEAMitUP project is based on an online platform that allows partner organizations to customize tools, activities and resources needed for each school. The platform serves as a "one-stop-shop" for teaching and learning to use innovative learning tools to teach STEAM and develop basic skills in students (problem solving, creativity, self-esteem), loaded with best practices, lesson plans, workshops and video guidelines. Each school can customize its programme and download it.
- **STEAMitUP Toolbox.** It includes a set of learning resources and pedagogic material built around challenges.
- **Didactic activities.** The project activities make use of robotics and other practical and innovative 21st century digital tools.
- **Learning.** The project follows a systematic approach involving all target groups. Therefore, a group of educators will be generated and trained on how to use robotics and other tools to actively encourage and engage learners to develop basic skills and competences and to thrive in the digital world. In this sense, blended learning modules (face-to-face and online for teachers) are developed to build their capacity on how they can use robotics and other digital artefacts in their classroom for STEAM education.
- **Didactic material.** It includes lesson plans, workshops, thematic school days, materials for the development of students' skills through interactive activities for students. This section also gives special relevance to the visibility of women and girls in science, providing materials, specific celebrations, etc. The material will be available for different age groups, from primary to secondary level. Teachers and schools will be able to adapt the project material to their national context and to the specific needs of their students.

3. STEAMY-WONDERS

STEAMY-WONDERS has as its main objective the promotion of women's participation in science careers. As mentioned in the introduction to this paper, STEAM (**Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics**) is still a male-dominated field. This project, through a compendium of Interactive Infographics, aims to motivate girls in STEAM careers, in addition to developing their capacity in each of the areas that are integrated and making visible some of the world's benchmarks in the world of science. In addition, the project also consists of a teacher training programme in the use and creation of infographics and a MOOC that collects all the results generated during the project.

The partner countries of this project are Croatia, Ireland, Germany, Cyprus, Czech Republic, and Spain, namely the following organizations:

- CALLIDUS (Croatia)
- Spectrum Research Centre (Ireland)
- Skills Elevation FHB (Germany)
- SYNTHESIS (Cyprus)
- BFI (Austria)
- JAITEK TECNOLOGÍA Y FORMACIÓN SL (Spain)
- ALIANCE LEKTORU a KONZULTANTU (Czech Republic)

The objectives of the STEAMY WONDER project are to:

- Promote a culture of scientific thinking among women, using evidence-based reasoning in decision-making, especially with regard to career planning.
- Provide appropriate and tangible case studies to ensure that women have the confidence to participate in an increasingly complex scientific and technological world.
- Develop a set of tailor-made resources for women that address problem-solving skills, innovation, analytical thinking, critical thinking, spatial awareness.
- Provide guidelines for human resource managers to enable gender-neutral recruitment, retention and promotion in the STEAM sector.

To this end, the following lines of action are proposed:

- Challenge-based resource generation for women in STEAM disciplines.
- Training for vocational training teachers.
- Toolkit for Human Resource Managers

- Steamy Wonders MOOC and Community of Practice

Among other products generated by the project, a compendium of Interactive Infographics presented in the form of posters with QR codes is proposed. Each of the infographics is composed of 4 elements, presented in the form of QR codes, which work on one of the areas that make up STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics). The QR codes are linked to digital learning materials that encourage users to interact with the information and learning content.

In addition, there is a strong emphasis on training Vocational Education and Training (VET) teachers in the use and creation of Interactive Infographics. To this end, STEAMY-WONDERS proposes a training programme for VET teachers to support them in the use of Infographics in their teaching practice in order to promote female participation in science careers. In addition, the programme also encourages training in the creation of materials so that teachers can create their own resources and can continue to extend this type of teaching.

In addition, the project develops a **MOOC** in which vocational tutors, support staff in companies, industrial relations professionals and young employees can access all learning materials developed in the STEAMY-WONDERS project.

4. iMAS

iMAS is a project whose main objective is to help teachers to know the evolution of their students' learning in the areas of mathematics, as well as to offer online resources to use with their students. In addition, teachers will have access to training courses, together with advice during the activities carried out in the project.

The partner countries that make up the iMAS consortium are Spain, the Netherlands, Belgium, Cyprus, and Ireland. Specifically, the participating organizations are the following:

- Universidad de Málaga (Spain)
- PRO WORK (Netherland)
- ARTEVELDEHOGESCHOOL (Belgium)
- CARDET (Cyprus)
- FIPL (Ireland)
- JAITEK Tecnología y Formación SL (Spain)

The objectives of the iMAS project are:

- To provide teachers with a statistical data tool to automate measures of mathematical learning progress, reducing the time spent on administration and transferring it to teaching informed by empirical test data.
- To increase levels of digital literacy in schools so that people become more self-reliant in the use of technology and less dependent on formal retraining whenever there is a change in the technology ecosystem.
- To develop a strategy to support the development of open educational resources, including free services based on a sustainable business model that is self-sustaining.
- To gather empirical evidence of what children know and can do in mathematics to feedback and develop the curriculum based on direct evidence.
- To provide a teaching resource that showcases best practice in mathematics teaching, including schemes of work, lesson plans and other resources.

In order to achieve these objectives, IMAS is therefore composed of 4 fundamental pillars: Training, Repository, Baseline Tests, and Statistics generated.

1. Training

The online training consists of 5 courses which, on the one hand, will enable teachers to learn new methodological models adapted to the cooperative and integrated work of students and, on the other hand, to make mathematics education more visible among the female sector in order to encourage girls to **choose science careers**.

2. Repository

The project proposes a repository of online resources classified using a taxonomy developed by the project that allows **searches** to be **tailored to specific needs**. The repository contains a wide variety of resources and activities for use with students.

3. Baseline Tests (BLT)

This project proposes a series of tests divided by levels (EQF1-primary, EQF2-secondary, EQF3-baccalaureate), which cover 6 different areas of mathematics: Algebra, Geometry, Statistics and Probability, Arithmetic, Number Theory and Calculus and Analysis. These tests are not evaluations, as all the tests at each level have the same difficulty, but they allow us to know the evolution of the students' learning both at group and personal levels, being able to detect the areas where they are having more difficulties and therefore intensify these areas with the resources proposed by the system as well as those proposed by the teacher. The idea is to carry out tests approximately **every five months**.

4. Statistics

Teachers will obtain the exact results of their students' level, both at an individual level (by students) and at a group level (class). They will also be able to visualize the evolution of their students' learning as they periodically complete more tests. On the other hand, in an **aggregated and anonymous** way, researchers will be able to find statistics at both national and European levels.

Results and Conclusions

The following are the results obtained to date from the Science for Fun project, as it is the most advanced one, where pilots have already taken place, and so far 2,471 users have participated, of which 2,361 are students and 85 are teachers. Teachers get all the data about the evolution of their students in the Learning Platform (<https://learning.science4fun.eu/>) where all the Base Line Tests and are, together with the rest of services as recommendations of resources from the project repository, or several courses about tools, methodologies and women visualization in Science. Data are presented in detailed tables, where teachers can select the way to present the data using the variables (Sex, EQF, Grade, Student, Area and Topic).

A sample Group Report is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Sample Data Details Table of Four Students

DATA DETAILS

Sex		EQF	
Grade			
Student	Area	Topic	Total
<input type="checkbox"/> S4F User, Student 050027 (ES) (Student ID:645)	<input type="checkbox"/> Astronomy		10.00
	<input type="checkbox"/> Biology	Botanics	0.00
		Cellular structure	10.00
		Genetics	10.00
		Zoology	10.00
		Total	7.50
	<input type="checkbox"/> Chemistry		7.50
	<input type="checkbox"/> Environmental resources		2.50
	<input type="checkbox"/> Geology		7.50
	<input type="checkbox"/> Physics		2.50
	Total		6.25
<input type="checkbox"/> S4F User, Student 050028 (ES) (Student ID:646)			7.71
<input type="checkbox"/> S4F User, Student 050029 (ES) (Student ID:647)			6.25
<input type="checkbox"/> S4F User, Student 050030 (ES) (Student ID:648)			6.25

And teachers are able to see the global situation of their groups and how that compares to the school, the region, the country and all the countries, as can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2

Radar Figures for My Group and Other Groups and Countries

And they can also check on the evolution of a concrete student, both graphically (Figure 3), but also in a table as seen before.

Figure 3

Evolution of learning for one student

EQF: 3

Number of tests: 2
Average Grade: 4.17
Max Grade: 5
Min Grade: 3.33

In all the other projects, the pilots have not started and are planned for October 2021. In all of them courses for teachers have been developed together with different OERs to be used by students.

In the case of IMAS, results will be looking similar to Science for Fun ones, but in this case, dealing with Mathematics instead.

As a general conclusion, it is necessary to incorporate actions to support and improve STEAM learning, especially focusing on the gender gap. It is almost certain that the future will be technological so, if we want to generate a more equitable and fair world, we must incorporate the gender perspective in STEAM learning.

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